

Cryptorchidism and Inguinal Hernia in Adult; A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Cryptorchidism, defined as undescended testicles, is the most prevalent congenital condition involving male genitalia, characterized by the absence of at least one testicle within the scrotum. Manifests unilaterally or bilaterally. Approximately 3% of full-term and 30% of premature male infants are born with undescended testicles. Untreated cryptorchidism can lead to potential complications such as infertility, testicular cancer, testicular torsion and even inguinal hernias.

Objective: Analyze the clinical characteristics, diagnostic methods and therapeutic strategies cryptorchidism in adults based on evidence published over the last decade

Method

A review was conducted based on an extensive PubMed search using the terms “bilateral,” “unilateral,” “cryptorchidism,” and “adulthood,” published between 2016 to 2026. Studies addressing the diagnosis, management, and outcomes of patients with such pathology.

Case report: A 39-year-old male patient presented to medical consultation after being referred for evaluation by general surgery due to inguinal unilateral hernia in the left region accompanied by cryptorchidism and a progressive increase in volume in that same inguinal side.

Conclusion: Cryptorchidism in adults is not a rare condition surrounded by a complex pathophysiology, economic and care services access, this is due not for a late diagnosis but because of a lack or lost surveillance, ending up in an adulthood with compromised reproductive function and/or high risk of testicular cancer.

Published On:
30 April

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Cryptorchidism is the most prevalent congenital abnormality involving male genitalia, is characterized by the absence of at least 1 testicle from the scrotum. Approximately 3% of full-term and 30% of premature male infants are born with 1 or both testicles undescended.(1) Testicular descent typically occurs by the seventh month of gestation. However, around 80% of cryptorchid testes descend within the first 3 months after birth, reducing the true incidence to approximately 1%.(2) In the US, cryptorchidism ranges from approximately 3% at birth to 1% from 1 year to adulthood. Globally, the prevalence varies, starting at around 4% to 5% at birth, decreasing to about 1% to 1.5% at age 3 months, and further decreasing to 1% to 2.5% at 9 months. This elevated prevalence highlights the significance of closely monitoring testicular development and considering timely interventions when necessary. (1) Cryptorchidism can manifest unilaterally or bilaterally, with a higher frequency of involvement observed in the right testicle. Bilateral cryptorchidism

is observed in approximately 10% of all patients with undescended testicles. (1)

Spontaneous descent is unlikely if the testis has not descended by 6 months, and surgical correction should be considered.(3). Without surgical intervention, an undescended testicle will likely descend during the initial 3 months of life. However, if undescended testes persist, it is advisable to perform an orchiopexy between the ages of 6 and 18 months to reposition the testes into the scrotum, thereby reducing risks and minimizing the potential for infertility.(1) Testicle can be situated anywhere along the descent pathway, showcasing a variety of characteristics such as dysgenetic, ectopic, hypoplastic, positioned high in the abdomen near the inguinal ring, found within the inguinal canal, or missing entirely. Unilateral presentation is common, occurring in two-thirds of cases. (4)

Undescended testes can lead to potential long-term complications, including decreased fertility (particularly if affecting both testicles), an increased risk of testicular germ cell tumors (with an overall risk of less than 1%), testicular

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torsion, inguinal hernias, and psychological issues if left untreated. (1) Approximately 10% to 30% of individuals with unilateral undescended testis may experience infertility, with the risk escalating from 35% to 65% or higher for those with bilateral disease. If bilateral cryptorchid testes are left untreated, the infertility rate can exceed 90%. (1)

Cryptorchidism is associated with male infertility in adulthood, primarily due to poor semen quality, which can be linked to compromised Sertoli cell function and its impact on Leydig cell function. (5) Cryptorchidism, hypospadias, testicular cancer, and poor semen quality collectively constitute testicular dysgenesis syndrome. This syndrome is believed to result from harmful environmental factors that disrupt embryonal programming and gonadal development during fetal life. (1)

Birth weight is the primary risk factor for undescended testes, followed by family history (heritability in first-degree male relatives is estimated to be around 0.5% to 1%). Additionally, 7% of siblings of boys with undescended testes also experience cryptorchidism, emphasizing its potential genetic predisposition within families. (1)

Other potential contributing risk factors include; alcohol consumption during pregnancy (5 or more drinks per week, which can increase the risk up to 3 times), chemical endocrine disruptors, cigarette smoking, congenital malformation syndromes; Down syndrome, Prader-Willi syndrome, and Noonan syndrome, exposure to phthalates, family history of cryptorchidism, ibuprofen use, In vitro fertilization, maternal diabetes, maternal exposure to diethylstilbestrol, maternal obesity, Persistent Müllerian duct syndrome, pesticide

CLINICAL CASE

A 39-year-old male patient with no chronic disease history, with the only antecedent since late childhood within surveillance from pediatric service with latest report as retractile testis, lost access to healthcare services, then regained it at the age of 35, comes referred to the medical consultation from urology service because of cryptorchidism and a non complicated left inguinal hernia. The latter begins about 10 months ago, after being moving multiple bags of cement, resulting in a progressive mass, non tender, non suppurative, that exacerbated with Valsalva maneuver and no changes in evacuations. In physical exploration, within reach of primary and secondary sexual characteristics. In scrotum area, an absent left testis, with a dilated deep inguinal ring, the no descended testis being unreachable by maneuvering. In the right side of the scrotum, testis presence within in range measurements for the male by age, with no dilated deep inguinal ring and without another changes after Valsalva maneuvers. Laboratory findings B- human chorionic gonadotropin hormone, AFP and LDH within normal ranges. On imaginary studies ultrasound; without identification of left testis at least on inguinal and scrotal area, no adenomegalies, no hydrocele, dilation of deep inguinal ring with spontaneous exit of preperitoneal fat. On the abdominal

exposure, preeclampsia (especially in its more severe forms, poses an increased risk of cryptorchidism), premature infants born before the descent of the testicles, Small for gestational-age infants and Smaller placental weight (1,2,3)

Within cryptorchidism two factors rise up, infertility and cancer. (1)

Hyperthermia is an important factor in fertility, which can impair spermatogenesis, as the intrascrotal temperature is several degrees cooler than ectopic positions. In some cases, accidental injury to the vas deferens, epididymis, or testis may occur during orchiopexy procedures. A higher incidence of anti-sperm antibodies exists in infertile patients with a history of cryptorchidism. (6) Specifically, approximately 10% to 30% of patients with a unilateral cryptorchid testicle will develop infertility, and azoospermia is found in 13% of individuals with unilateral undescended testicles. In contrast, azoospermia rates can increase to around 90% in patients with untreated bilateral cryptorchidism. (6)

The risk of testicular cancer is approximately 3 times higher than that of the general population when orchiopexy is performed before puberty, this risk increases to 5 to 6 times higher when orchiopexy is conducted after puberty. The timing of orchiopexy, whether in early infancy or later in childhood, does not appear to significantly affect the risk of developing testicular cancer. (7)

Being seminoma as the most prevalent type of testicular cancer found in untreated undescended testes, with the peak age range for this tumor occurring between the ages of 15 and 45. (1)

tomography doesn't describe it as intrabdominal testicle but only preperitoneal fat at left indirect inguinal hernia. On the tomography slices can view the no descended testis over the inguinal canal.

Figure 1: Left cryptorchid testis over the left inguinal canal

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The surgery was planned as an ordinary open lichtenstein hernioplasty, with incision through the skin on left inguinal area, at the moment of identifying indirect hernia sac and reduce it, the testis comes to the plane with all his elements, this testis with atrophic and reduced dimensions. (Figure 2).

Being the contralateral testis healthy, a classic orchidectomy was made, due to dilated deep inguinal ring, the hernioplasty was made with mesh, covering all the defects and thus closing fascias including skin.

Figure 2: Atrophic and small cryptorchid testis

In the postoperative time, the patient does not course with hematoma, hemocele or reactive hydrocele, surgery site without any early complication, then was discharged with follow-up and surveillance by urology within histopathology result.

DISCUSSION

A review was made based on an extensive PubMed search using the terms “bilateral,” “cryptorchidism,” and “adult,” and 92 articles were found. Narrowing search by excluding articles that were published no more than 10 years ago, excluding articles that were not in the English language, articles that did not specify the age of patients, and articles that were non relevant to the main pathology. Then refining the PubMed search, using the terms “unilateral,” “adult,” “cryptorchidism,” “orchidopexy,” and “orchidectomy,” 21 articles were found, excluding using the same previous cited criteria.

In the articles that were reviewed, 10 case reports of adult bilateral cryptorchidism, with an average age of diagnosis and intervention at 31.8 years. (8). In four of the 10 cases, the cryptorchid testes were located in the inguinal canal, in five cases, cryptorchid testes were located intra-abdominally, and in one case, one was inguinal while the other was intra-abdominal. Seven of the 10 individuals were infertile and all seven were found to have cryptorchid testes. (8). Although the risk of testicular cancer is decreased with earlier correction of chryptochidism, performing an orchiopey does not completely eliminate the risk of cancer. For this reason,

as well as the low fertility potential in a UDT, orchiectomy may be the superior method of intervention for patients with cryptorchidism, especially in adult patients where the testes were in the cryptorchid position for a longer duration. (8) On contrast with another single center experience them found that most adult patients had unilateral cryptorchidism, which was palpable before the surgical procedure, but all the cryptorchid testes were smaller than the contralateral testes. The location of the cryptorchid testis in the operation was mostly in the inguinal area. The clinical characteristics in adult cryptorchidism seem to be similar to those of child cryptorchidism. (9) They did not find any case with testis malignancy during the follow-up duration of 61.4 ± 41.4 months (7~132 months) after desired orchiopey even knowing the possible malignancies. (9) Also In terms of paternity, in cases with unilateral cryptorchidism, the study demonstrated that all of the 12 patients who underwent a testis biopsy had abnormal histologic findings. Three of the 4 patients who underwent the preoperative semen analysis showed abnormal findings. However, 4 of the 6 married patients had children. On the other hand, all of the patients with bilateral cryptorchidism showed abnormal findings in the testis histology and the semen analysis, and had no children.(9) In them study, only two patients who presented unilateral, non-palpable testis, both of whom were married and had fathered a child, under went orchiectomy. As stated, orchiopey did not provide advantages to the adult cryptorchid patients. However, most adult patients at least in Korea seemed to prefer orchiopey to avoid the negative perception of emasculation. This may reflect the psychic

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trauma they anticipated experiencing after an orchiectomy. In addition, our patients did not have any malignancy or complication after orchiopexy. Therefore, we concluded that the orchiopexy in adult cryptorchidism may be a legitimate option for management respecting the patient's preference.(9) As the extensive review of some series of cases, concluded that as in the present clinical case, the decision is foremost by patient and psychological context, but as with this male patient clinical case, that has family and achieved secondary sexual characteristics, he accepted the decision of orchidectomy even before the surgery based on personal preference more than preventive action. Also within the Cito's approach (TESE) testicular Sperm extraction, opens a broad possibility to achieve the best treatment based on sperm viability between long term orchidopexy VS orchidectomy on adult males. (10) The AUA Guidelines suggests the orchidectomy on postpuberal males, inferring same treatment in adulthood, this decision based on evidence that the majority cannot contribute to fertility and have significant malignant potential even possibility of undergo torsion. (11,12)

CONCLUSIONS

Current recommendations are that cryptorchid testes be surgically corrected by age one to two to reduce the risk of infertility and testicular cancer. For postpubertal children, the American Urological Association guidelines recommend orchiectomy once again. However, as the actual review state claims that personal decision will be made, the evidence says that in context of male with unilateral cryptorchidism, inguinal hernia satisfied parity and achieved secondary sexual characteristics, the best decision will be the orchidectomy, filling the resolution between testicular cancer prevention and hernia treatment. Cryptorchid testes remain undiagnosed during the pediatric period, causing patients to present in adulthood. Due to its less frequency in the adult population and lack of long published data, no society guidelines currently exist regarding the management in adulthood, surgical correction, and postoperative follow-up of adult orchidectomy in terms of cryptorchidism. Opening a broad area of investigation that can be of benefit in this specific male population.

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